

THE PLACE AND ROLE OF THE CHAIR AND THRESHOLD COMPOSITION IN THE NATIONAL STYLE ARCHITECTURE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ARCHITECTURE OF THE BANQUET HALL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7703543>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 24th February 2023

Accepted: 06th March 2023

Online: 07th March 2023

KEY WORDS

Banquet hall, foundations, walls, curtain walls, national architect, modern architecture.

ABSTRACT

In this article, one of the priorities today is the development of our national values. Tourists coming to our country from all over the world are interested in the architectural monuments and traditions of Uzbekistan and seeing them with their own eyes makes a good impression on them. Foreign guests sometimes visit the clubs to see our traditions and participate in them. Here they watch performances in the entertainment venues and praise the Uzbek national entertainments. Another example: today, one is dazzled by the multi-story buildings and houses being built in all regions and cities of Uzbekistan. After the construction of such houses, of course, there will be a need for public dining facilities and entertainment facilities.

The materials of this article are of great importance in decorating public catering buildings in national style, that is, enriching them with national patterns and compositions, building them in historical styles and adapting them to local weather and climate conditions. Its scientific importance lies in the absence of scientific works, literature, regulatory requirements and documents about the architecture of catering and recreation buildings today.

Nowadays, the number of European catering establishments, restaurants, coffee shops, bars, phytobars is increasing. However, it is admirable to see the events typical of our traditions at the parties held in Uzbekistan. It is to create the theoretical and practical basis of designing the new national style, historical and modern artistic aesthetic requirements, which are compatible with our traditions, and convey to the people the design architects.

Architectural decorations should be processed in accordance with building forms: the harmony of architectural forms in the composition should play a primary role, and decorations should play a secondary role. The composition of decorations should be made of the main and auxiliary (filler) patterns. It is desirable that the main patterns are intended to

be seen from a distance, and their assistants, acting as a background, are intended to be seen up close.

Pattern harmony should be based on ratio, distribution, rhythm, scale grid, symmetry and color contrast. Decorations are divided into majestic wall paintings, brickwork, tilework, ganchkori, girix, Islamic, script, carving, muqarnas and kundal types. All patterns must have modular scale and geometric design styles and unique color schemes.

It is not too late to see, calculate and recognize these parts and forms of buildings as the most important artistic structural factors of architectural composition in the creation of

architecture. Over the centuries, these issues have been gradually understood and recognized, and their contemporary, positive and temporary traditions have been formed.

Catering buildings and wedding halls are being built not only in cities, but also in rural areas these days. It can be said that their construction has acquired a mass character. However, today there are no regulatory documents or construction rules regarding the strength, construction, and location of banquet halls' architecture and buildings. On top of that, no scientific or practical literature has been developed, which sheds light on such buildings, especially the architecture and architectural-planning solutions of the entertainment centers. Filling this gap in the science of architecture, explaining it in a reasonable way is the main issue and scientific hypothesis of this article.

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Catering buildings and wedding halls are being built not only in cities, but also in rural areas these days. It can be said that their construction has acquired a mass character. However, no regulatory documents or construction rules have been developed today

regarding the strength, construction, and location of the buildings and structures of the gymnasiums. On top of that, no scientific or practical literature has been developed, which sheds light on such buildings, especially the architecture and architectural-planning solutions of the entertainment centers. Filling this gap in the science of architecture, explaining it in a reasonable way is the main issue and scientific hypothesis of this dissertation.

Banquet halls differ from other catering buildings in that their capacity is designed for at least 500 seats at a time. This requires that the building be beautiful, strong and convenient for use in all respects, provide quick and quality service to guests, arrange their cars in an orderly manner, and be resistant to events such as fire and earthquake.

It is necessary to regulate the distance between the red line of the street and the building line of the main facade of the club. Based on our observation, we suggest that this distance should be defined as a minimum of 12 meters and a maximum of 24 meters after the red line.

Due to our independence, the increase in the welfare of our people and the expansion of economic opportunities are observed in the restoration of our ancient values in the family structure of our children, and in this connection, the needs for entertainment are increasing. Today, the construction of banquet halls not only in cities, but also in villages is a proof of our opinion. This, in turn, raises the problems of scientific determination of modern urban planning, architectural and artistic-aesthetic requirements in the formation of the architecture of entertainment centers and their implementation into practice among the urgent problems of the architecture of the Republic of Independence.

In fact, banquet halls as separate buildings did not exist in the architectural typology of the former Soviet Union. They came into being only as a product of the socio-economic development of the Independence period and took their rightful place in the typology of modern buildings.

With the socio-cultural and material development of our society and the revival of our national traditions and their transformation into modern national values, today's bars have become the most prestigious public buildings of our cities and villages, occupying the position of an important architectural and urban planning object. In this regard, great attention is being paid to the question of their location in the structure of cities and villages, that is, from the point of view of urban planning, in which part of the settlement they should be properly located and built. In addition to the fact that each club owner separates his object from other buildings and buildings in architecturally solemn, significant, luxurious, attention-grabbing volume-architectural solutions, it is convenient for visitors to come and go to clubs, and most of them are located in the most prestigious parts of the city. -tirish, and the building of the gymnasium is trying to be placed as close as possible to the main highways of the city.

Our research and observations showed that when placing wedding halls in the urban structure, the customers mainly tried to take into account and consider the most important situations in the tune:

- placement of entertainment centers within microdistricts or residential areas as much as possible in their central part, that is, in the most popular places where people's attention is drawn;
 - proximity of the location of the entertainment center to city transport and highways, highways;
 - next to the location of the entertainment center, there is a possibility to organize parking lots for guests' personal vehicles and cars;
 - the maximum visibility of the building of the gymnasium from the main streets of the city, the presence of a large space in front of it, necessary for the gathering of people;
 - the location of the shopping center should not be close to large markets or industrial enterprises, communal-economic buildings, railways and stations.
- At the same time, through the natural analysis we conducted, it became clear that some clubs, such as "Astoria" in Samarkand, "Grand" and "Alpomish" wedding halls in Jizzakh, are located very close to the city streets, and in front of them, in order to wait until the wedding hall opens, absence or lack of required space was observed. Such a situation can create very dangerous situations for

street transport and wedding guests, especially when the bride and groom's crew can be stopped in front of the wedding hall and create a "traffic jam" on the street.

In a number of other entertainment venues, for example, "Boghishamol", "Karvan-saroy" in Samarkand, etc., the area in front of the front facade of the entertainment venue has turned into a parking lot for the cars of wedding guests.

In order to prevent such unpleasant situations, it is necessary to adjust the distance between the red line of the street and the building line of the main facade of the wedding hall. Based on our observations, we suggest that this distance be defined as a minimum of 12 meters and a maximum of 24 meters after the red line.

Today, it is difficult to imagine the architecture of modern public buildings of the city and region of Samarkand without newly built and under-construction bazams, that is, bazams. They play an important role in the formation of street architecture, because most of them are built with the main facade facing the street, and in most cases they are two-story.

The architecture of such buildings can be divided into three groups according to their appearance:

- Entertainment centers built entirely on the basis of the traditions of our national architecture;
- Gymnasiums built on the principles (styles) of modern architecture;
- Banquet halls with mixed architecture;

The architecture of the entertainment centers belonging to the first group is characterized by more national architectural forms and decorations, the facade mainly has tile-curling patterns, glazed majolica and rivets, and the roof has blue domes.

- proximity of the location of the entertainment center to city transport and highways, highways;
- next to the location of the entertainment center, there is a possibility to organize parking lots for guests' personal vehicles and cars;
- the maximum visibility of the building of the gymnasium from the main streets of the city, the presence of a large space in front of it, necessary for the gathering of people;
- the location of the shopping center should not be close to large markets or industrial enterprises, communal-economic buildings, railways and stations.

At the same time, through the natural analysis we conducted, it became clear that some clubs, such as "Astoria" in Samarkand, "Grand" and "Alpomish" wedding halls in Jizzakh, are located very close to the city streets, and in front of them, in order to wait until the wedding hall opens, absence or lack of required space was observed. Such a situation can create very dangerous situations for street transport and wedding guests, especially when the bride and groom's crew can be stopped in front of the wedding hall and create a "traffic jam" on the street.

The banquet halls of the second group are mainly characterized by wide glazed facades, the entrance part - the embossing of the "threshold", the chair, the body and the artistic finishing of the building with special attention.

A combination of the above qualities can be seen in the architecture of banquet halls of the third group.

Almost 70% of banquet halls have summer and winter banquet halls. In some banquet halls, even the area of the summer part is slightly larger than the winter hall.

Regarding the architecture of our banquet halls, it is necessary to say that the stylistic solution of the facade of some banquet halls does not correspond to the style of its interior, that is, the architecture of the main banquet hall. For example, this is the case at "Toychi Baba" and "Visol" parties, built a little later on the right side of the street. In our opinion, this is a negative quality. We believe that the facade of the building should match its interior.

Catering buildings and banquet halls are being built in large numbers not only in cities, but also in rural areas these days. It can be said that their construction has acquired a mass character. However, today there are no regulatory documents or construction rules for the strength, construction, and location of banquet halls and buildings. On top of that, no scientific or practical literature has been developed, which sheds light on such buildings, especially the architecture and architectural-planning solutions of banquet halls. Filling this gap in the science of architecture, explaining it scientifically is the main issue and scientific hypothesis of this article.

Banquet halls differ from other public catering buildings in that their capacity is designed for at least 500 seats at a time. This requires that the building be beautiful, strong and convenient for use in all respects, provide fast and quality service to guests, arrange their cars in an orderly manner, and build them to be resistant to events such as fire and earthquake.

The architecture of banquet halls and auditoriums was formed side by side with the architecture of the years of independence of our republic, and in terms of its content and form, it is precisely the interpretations of the national idea and the main concepts in the field of architecture: the reflection of function in form and volume, that is, the harmony of function and form, and their architectural image is being formed in accordance with the new outlook and aesthetic needs of people in the years of Independence - the new era, based on the aesthetic and architectural-artistic requirements for public-reputable buildings.

Visually noticeable architectural forms in the architecture of banquet hall buildings include:

- Building grade, i.e. its floor is significantly above the ground level and ensuring the majesty of the building;
- Exaggeration of the entrance part of the building, i.e. its processing in a visually festive architectural composition;
- The composition of the building body from architectural parts (windows, plasters) formed in horizontal metric rhythms.
- The complete part of the building of the banquet hall, i.e., the composition of the artistic completion, is processed with special attention;
- Building architecture-exterior and interior color gloss;
- The style of the banquet hall building is based on the law of symmetry in most cases;
- Proportion of the architectural forms of the building to each other and to the overall whole (the main volume of the building) is the provision of harmony, that is, compliance with the

overall law of the architectural composition of the building. To solve the problem of parking in banquet halls, it is advisable to build parking lots for the private cars of guests visiting the banquet hall next to or near the building of the banquet hall, on the right and left sides of the building. At least 12 square meters per car for parking area. space must be allocated. The parking area should also be greened in a metric row composition, cars should not be left in the sunlight.

In order to solve the problem of parking in clubs, it is advisable to build parking lots for the private cars of the guests visiting the clubs next to or near the building of the club, on the right and left sides of the building. At least 12 square meters per car for parking area. space must be allocated. The parking area should also be greened in a metric row composition, cars should not be left in the sunlight.

One of the biggest problems faced by our architects in the design of banquet hall buildings is the acoustics of banquet halls, i.e. the noise of the music and songs from the orchestra during the wedding (noise power 90-100 DBA) and the problem of reducing it and bringing it to a standard level.

There are several measures aimed at solving this problem, one of which is the method of architecturally planning the recreation hall, taking into account the noise propagation and its return echo state.

In one of the projects we offer, there is an architectural solution aimed at solving this problem in such a way, that is, the central part of the banquet halls is made with 2 lights and taken under a high dome. The noise of the orchestra and music in the banquet hall does not travel back into the hall, and in this way the noise level is greatly reduced. This is the first method.

The second method is to create a fountain in the center of the hall that flows from above, that is, from under the dome, in the form of small continuous drops. This method also reduces the sound wave in the hall to a certain extent by absorbing and absorbing it.

The third method is to cover the walls and windows of the banquet hall with a transparent material that absorbs and absorbs sound (for example, Knop's acoustic plasterboard).

The fourth method is to cover the front stage, where the orchestra and artists are located, with a flat flexible material, transparent, 1.5-2 meters high. I think that with the comprehensive application of these methods, the high noise level in the banquet hall can be reduced to a normal level, i.e. 39-45 DBA.

References:

1. Қосимова Ф.А., Юсупова Ш. Самарқанд шахрининг моддий маданияти тарихидан лавхалар.//Самарқанд шахрининг 2750 йиллиги ва СамДАҚИнинг 40 йиллигига бағишланган Республика назарий ва амалий конференция материаллари.–Самарқанд: СамДАҚИ, 2006.
2. Қосимова Ф.А. Самарқанд шахрининг мустақиллик даврида эришган ютуқлари.//СамДАҚИнинг 40 йиллигига бағишланган илмий тўплам.–Самарқанд, 2007.
3. Пардаев С. Атроф муҳит муҳофазасида дарахт ва буталарнинг роли.//Конференция материаллари. 2013 й.
4. Хабиб Темур. Самарқанд сайқали. Истиқлол берган имкон: қурилишда бурилиш. "Зарафшон" газетаси, 1995–йил 19–сентябр сони.
5. Уралов А.С., Рахимов А.К., Саидова Б.А. Архитектуравий композиция ва лойиҳалаш асослари.–Самарқанд, 2005.
6. Уралов А.С. Самарқанд шахрининг Мустақиллик йилларидаги архитектураси.//“Ўзбекистон архитектураси ва қурилиши” журнали, № 3, 2007.
7. Уралов А.С. Самарқанд шахрининг Мустақиллик йилларидаги архитектураси.–“Зарафшон”, № 16, 2007.
8. Уралов А.С., Қўшмонов Т.Ф. Бинолар типологияси.–Тошкент, 2013.
9. Akbarali, U. ., & Dilnoza, K. . (2022). National Culture of Banquet Hall Building Architecture and Principles of its Formation. International Journal of Culture and Modernity, 22, 31–40. Retrieved from <https://ijcm.academicjournal.io/index.php/ijcm/article/view/427>
10. Bolikulovich K. M., Pulatovich M. B. HEAT-SHIELDING QUALITIES AND METHODS FOR ASSESSING THE HEAT-SHIELDING QUALITIES OF WINDOW BLOCKS AND THEIR JUNCTION NODE WITH WALLS //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 11. – С. 829-840.
11. Pulatovich, M. B. . (2021). Energy Efficient Building Materials for External Walls of Residential Buildings Physical Properties of Heat. International Journal of Culture and Modernity, 9, 1–11. Retrieved from <https://ijcm.academicjournal.io/index.php/ijcm/article/view/67>
12. Pulatovich, M. B. . (2021). Analysis of Underground Projects of Energy-Efficient Residential Buildings. International Journal of Culture and Modernity, 9, 12–18. Retrieved from <https://ijcm.academicjournal.io/index.php/ijcm/article/view/68>
13. Pulatovich, M. B. ., & Innatillayevich, G. O. . (2021). Laboratory Experimental Studies on the Properties of Highly Sedimentary Lyos Soils when their Moisture Changes Over Time.

- European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630), 8, 91-98. Retrieved from <http://ejlss.indexedresearch.org/index.php/ejlss/article/view/119>
14. Pulatovich, M. B. , & Shodiyev, K. . (2021). Thermal Insulation of Basement Walls of Low-Rise Residential Buildings and Calculation of its Thickness. International Journal of Culture and Modernity, 9, 19-27. Retrieved from <https://ijcm.academicjournal.io/index.php/ijcm/article/view/69>
15. Матёкубов, Бобур Пўлатович, and Сарвара Музаффаровна Саидмуродова. "КАМ СУВ ТАЛАБЧАН БОҒЛОВЧИ АСОСИДАГИ ВЕРМИКУЛИТЛИ ЕНГИЛ БЕТОНЛАР ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИНИ ҚЎЛЛАНИЛИШИ." INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES. Vol. 1. No. 15. 2022.
16. Pulatovich, M. B. . (2021). Energy Efficient Building Materials for External Walls of Residential Buildings Physical Properties of Heat. International Journal of Culture and Modernity, 9, 1-11. Retrieved from <https://ijcm.academicjournal.io/index.php/ijcm/article/view/67>
17. Тулаков Э.С., Иноятлов Д., Қурбонов А.С., Матёкубов Б.П.. Бинолар-нинг ертўла деворларини иссиқлик изоляциялаш ва унинг қалинлигини ҳисоблаш. //Ме'морчилик ва қуриш муаммолари Проблемы архитектуры и строительства.Samarqand 2020. №4.(2-қисм) -С.29-32.
18. Inatillayevich G. O., Pulatovich M. B. Analysis of Underground Projects of Energy Efficient Low-Rise Residential Buildings Built on Highly Flooded Soils <https://doi.org/10.31149/ije.v4i9>. – Т. 2156.
19. Egamova Marguba Turakulovna, Matyokubov Bobur Pulatovich. (2023). WAYS TO INCREASE THE ENERGY EFFICIENCY OF BUILDINGS AND THEIR EXTERNAL BARRIER STRUCTURES. EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH, 3(1), 186-191. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7519183>